

TILNING IJTIMOY HAYOTDAGI O'RNI. TIL VA UNING BOSHQA TILLAR BILAN O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6589467>

ANNOTATSIYA. Ushbu maqolada tilning ijtimoiy hayotda tutgan o'rni, vazifalari haqidagi ma'lumotlar asosan keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: til, jamiyat, funksiya, ekstralingvistik, sotsialingvistika, artibutatsiya.

Til – bu ijtimoiy hodisa, u kishilik jamiyatining asosiy aloqa vositasi bo'lib, jamiyatga xizmat qiladi. Shuning uchun ham tilning kishilik jamiyatidagi roli beqiyos. Ma'lum vaqtga kelib yozuv yaratilganidan so'ng o'sha aloqa vositasi bõlgan tillar yozuvida aksini topgan. Tarixiy taraqqiyat jarayonida vujudga kelgan davlatlar yemirilishi bilan ularning aloqa vositasi bo'lgan tillar chunonchi, finiklar tili, lotin tili va boshqa eski tillar 9-10 asrgacha iste'molda bo'lib, keyin o'lik tillarga aylangan. Kishilik jamiyatining tarixiy taraqqiyoti davomida eng muhim aloqa vositasi bo'lgan til va uning xususiyatlari haqida turli tushunchalar, fikrlar va nazariyalar vujudga keldi. Ba'zi olimlar tilni hayvon, o'simlik kabi jonli narsalarga o'xshatib tabiatdagi tirik organizm deb tushungan va shunday da'vo qilishgan. Til ijtimoiy hodisa sifatida yaratilgandan beri, hayotning barcha bosqichlarida, til uzviy bog'liq jamiyat. Bu ulanish ikki tomonlama belgi: til jamiyatda va jamiyatdan tashqarida mavjud emas, mavjud bo'lolmaydi. Asosiy maqsad tili-vosita sifatida xizmat qilish odamlar o'rtasidagi aloqa. Til "faqat ehtiyoj, shoshilinch ehtiyoj tufayli yuzaga keladi boshqa odamlar bilan muloqot qilish". Rivojlanish bilan jamiyat shakllarining asoratlanishi jamoat hayoti va ongini boyitish, rivojlantirish rivojlanib murakkablashadi. Til jamiyat tomonidan ishlatiladigan til mutlaqo faoliyatning barcha sohalarida yashash uchun qulay jamiyat boshqa odamlar bilan suhbatlashish ommaviy zinapoyani yuqori ko'tarish, siz egalik qilishingiz kerak tili. Til boshqalar orasida alohida o'rin egallaydi, ijtimoiy tadbirlarda o'ynagan maxsus roli tufayli jamiyat. Umumiy narsa shundaki til- insonning mavjud bo'lishi va rivojlanishi uchun zarur shart jamiyat. Til xususiyatlari uning qonunlari faoliyat ko'rsatmoqda va tarixiy rivojlanish boshqalardan tubdan farq qiladi. Ijtimoiy tadbir. Artibutatsiya qilishga imkon beradigan asosiy xususiyat ijtimoiy hodisalar toifasiga kiruvchi til xizmat qilish qobiliyatiga aylanadi. Ammo til jamiyatga boshqacha

xizmat qiladi. Gap shundaki, til jamiyatga xizmat qiladi, o'z-o'zidan bu artibut uchun hal qiluvchi mezon emas, ijtimoiy hodisalar toifasiga kiruvchi til. Xizmatga jamiyat avtomobil qila oladi va hatto individual tabiiy hodisalar insonga xizmat qiladi. Barcha savol qanday bo'ladi til jamiyatga xizmat qiladi va unga qay darajada xizmat qiladi. Shu munosabat bilan uni biron bir bilan aniqlash mumkin emas ijtimoiy tadbirdan. Til bu na madaniyat shakli, na ma'lum bir sinf mafkurasi, yoki so'zning keng ma'nosida ustunlik emas. Til hayotdagi o'zgarishlarni aks ettirish qobiliyatiga ega jamiyatning barcha sohalarida bu uni boshqalardan ajratib turadiga narsa ijtimoiy tadbirlar. Eng jiddiy xususiyatlaridan biri uni sanashga imkon beradi ijtimoiy hodisa bu haqiqatga xizmat qiladi, jamiyat til yaratadi, yaratilganini nazorat qiladi va uni aloqa vositalari tizimiga o'rnatadi. Yaratish va shakllantirish huquqi til jamiyatga tegishli. Til jamiyatning mahsulidir, shu sababli bu nomga loyiqdir, ijtimoiy hodisa kòproq darajada boshqalarga qaraganda hodisa xizmat qiladi jamiyat.

Jamiyat – u yoki bu ijtimoiy, kasbiy, jinsi va yoshi etnik, etnografik, diniy guruhlariga mansub odamlar o'rtasidagi har xil munosabatlar tizimi, bunda har xil kishi o'z o'rnini egallaydi va shu sababli ma'lum bir shaxsning egasi sifatida ishlaydi. Til juda kòp funksiyalarga ega. Asosiy tilning vazifasi aloqa vositasi bo'lishi kerak. Asosiysiga til xususiyatlari kommunikativ, kognitiv, kumulatifni o'z ichiga oladi. Til bu odamlarga bir-birini tushunish, inson faoliyatining barcha sohalarida qo'shma ishlarni yo'lga qo'yish imkoniyatini beradi.

1. Kommunikativ til funksiyasi-asosiy til funksiyasi.

Til paydo bo'ldi va mavjud odamlar muloqot qilishi uchun. Axborot bu tushunarli va murojaat qilingan odamning xulq-atvori uchun muhim bo'lgan ma'lumotlar. Nutq ma'lumotni odamdan odamga yetkazish vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Bu funksiyada nutqni amalga oshirish mumkin bo'ladi, chunki ma'lumot nutqda, unda ishlatiladigan so'zlarda saqlanishi mumkin. So'zlar almashish, ularni ma'lum bir ma'lumotni o'z ichiga olgan tushunchalar sifatida qabul qilish orqali odamlar shu so'zlardagi bilimlarni almashadilar. Bir-birlari bilan muloqot qilish, odamlar o'zlarining fikrlari, his-tuyg'ulari, hissiy tajribalari, irodani ifodalash bir-biriga ma'lum bir yo'nalishda harakat qilish erishish o'zaro tushunish.

2. Kognitiv til funksiyasi.

Atrofdagi olamni bilish, o'rganish asosan foydalanish orqali amalga oshiradi. Aloqa odamlar atrofidagi voqelik haqida ma'lum bilimlarni o'z ichiga oladi va dunyoni bilishning universal va samarali vositalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Shunday qilib til kognitiv yoki kognitivni amalga oshiradi.

3. Kumulyativ (jamg'arma) til funksiyasi.

Ushbu til funksiyasida avlodlar o'rtasidagi bo'g'in vazifasini bajaradi, xizmat qiladi. Eng aniq to'plangan funksiyasi lug'at sohasida o'zini namoyon qiladi, chunki obyektlar bilan bevosita bog'liqdir, hodisalar atrofdagi voqelik. Kumulatif funksiya aks ettirishdir, tuzatish va saqlash lingvistik shaxs tomonidan qamrab olingan faoliyat to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar, ma'lum bir etnolingvistik, madaniy barcha a'zolari tomonidan olinadigan dunyo haqidagi ma'lumotlar birligi, odamlarning lingvistik jamoasi. Tasniflash masalasida har xil fikrlarga qaramay til xususiyatlari, barcha tadqiqotchilar bir ovozdan ikkita shubhasiz muhim ekanligiga rozi bo'lishadi, vazifalari qaysi til insoniyat hayotida amalga oshadi – kognitiv va kommunikativ.

Vaqlar til faqat ichida mavjud jamiyat unga bog'liq emas. Rivojlanish jamiyatning rivojlanish jarayonini rag'batlantiradi til tezlikni tezlashtiradi yoki pasaytiradi tilning o'zgarishi, ba'zi ishtirokchilarni qayta tashkil etishga hissa qo'shadi til tizimi, ularni yangi elementary bilan boyitish. Til davlat shakliga va iqtisodiy shakllanishlarning xususiyatlariga bog'liq. Har biri ijtimoiy- iqtisodiy shakllanish ma'lum bir turmush tarzini yaratadi jamiyatning, bu bitun bir-biriga bog'liq bo'lgan kompleksda o'zini namoyon qiladi hodisalar. Jamiyat hech qachon mutlaqo bir xil jamoa emas va hech qachon bo'lmaydi. Unda sabablarga ko'ra farqalanish mavjud. Bu keyinchalik sinfda, mulkda va kasbda asosda bo'linish bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan til.

Rivojlanishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tili bor:

Media doirasida o'zgargan tili, fanning rivojlanishi, omma harakati, yangi davlatchilikning vujudga kelishi, qonun hujjatlari va hujjatlarning shakllarini o'zgartirish va boshqalar. Ushbu omillarning ta'siri til har xil va shaklda va kuchda. Bu ba'zi bir dialektizmlar va argotizmlarning adabiy lug'at tomonidan o'zlashtirilishiga olib keladi. Misollar: yetishmovchilik, nosozlik, kamon va boshqalar. Yangi sinonimiklar mavjud darajalari: aloqa-alloqa-birlashma-ta'zim va boshqalar.

Xuddi shunday bilvosita, rivojlanishga ta'sir qilish qiyin tili va boshqalar ijtimoiy omillar. Uning tarkibiy qismlarini rivojlantirishning muhim bosqichlaridan biri funksional-kommunikativ

tizimlar kapitalistikdan o'tish jamiyat sotsialistikaga madaniyat o'sishi, rivojlanishi savodxonlik, majburiy o'rta ta'lim adabiy tashuvchilar doirasini kengaytiradi, til va uning tarkibi va boshqa tarkibiy qismlar bilan aloqalarida aks etadi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris "Devonu lugotit turk" in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel "Between Two Doors", one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik,” og’ir dard,” yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O’ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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